

**INDIGOID VAT DYES OF THE ISATIN SERIES. PART VI.
3-INDOLE-2'-(7'-CHLORO) THIONAPHTHENE-INDIGOS**

BY SISIR KUMAR GUHA AND JNANENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE

7-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene has been condensed with isatin and a few of its substituted products. The 3-indole-2'-(7'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigos are found to be lighter than their parent substances and the corresponding 5'-chloro compounds. The preparation and the properties of 7:7'-dichlorothioindigo have been studied.

In part V of this series of papers (Guha and Basu-Mallick, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 214), the effect of a chlorine atom was studied when present in the 5'-position of the thionaphthene ring of 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo (Thioindigo scarlet-R) and some of its substituted products (Ciba Red G etc.).

The present investigation was undertaken with the idea of studying the effect of a chlorine atom in the 7'-position of the thionaphthene-indigos. The primary aim is to make a complete study of the influence of a chlorine atom when present in all the available positions of the thionaphthene ring of 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigos.

With this object in view, 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Dalglish and Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 893) has been condensed with isatin and some of its substituted products and another new series of asymmetrical thioindigoid dyes has been obtained having the general constitutional formula (I).

(I)

These vat dyes are darkish red, deep red and violet-red crystalline substances, the yield of each of which is quite high, varying between 80 and 90% of the theoretical value. All of them melt above 320°. They are soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene. The parent substance and its 5-chloro-, and 5-bromo-substituted compounds are sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, whereas the dibromo-, bromonitro-, and dinitro-substituted dyes are insoluble in the same solvent. The last three dyes are also insoluble in alcohol. The dyeing shades of all these products have been uniformly developed on wool from a dilute sulphuric acid bath and on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. The colour of the vat, which was obtained at 65°-70°, is yellow in every case except the dinitro compound whose vat is brownish yellow, from which the original colour of all the dyes reappears on atmospheric oxidation.

It has been observed that these dyeing shades are lighter in colour than those developed from the corresponding 5'-chloro compounds (Guha and Basu-Mallick, *loc. cit.*) and their parent substances, pointing to the conclusion that the change in colour is

in the order : 5'-chloro compound > parent compound > 7'-chloro compound. In Table I, the dyeing shades on cotton obtained from the compounds of these three series have been laid down for comparison.

TABLE I
T = Thionaphthene-indigo.

Compounds.	Dyeing shades on cotton.
3-Indole-2'-T	Scarlet-red
3-Indole-2'-(5'-chloro)-T	Deep red
3-Indole-2'-(7'-chloro)-T	Darkish red
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-T	Yellowish red
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(5'-chloro)-T	Violet-red
3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(7'-chloro)-T	Violet-red (lighter shade)
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-T	Dark red
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(5'-chloro)-T	Deep violet-red
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(7'-chloro)-T.	Darkish violet-red

Dalgliesh and Mann (*loc. cit.*) related 7:7'-dichlorothioindigo but the details of its preparation, its chemical and dyeing properties and melting point were not recorded. This compound was required for studying the change in colour of the isomeric dichlorothioindigos. It is a violet-red needle shaped dye and lighter in shade than its isomeride, 5:5'-dichlorothioindigo.

One of the present authors (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 20 ; 1943, 20, 37) prepared a pure specimen of 4-methyl-, and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene, m. p. 75-76° and 80-81° respectively. Dalgliesh and Mann (*loc. cit.*) prepared these compounds by different methods and recorded m. p. 65-66° and 73-78° respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Indole-2'-(7'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigo.—Isatin (1.029 g.) was dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (1.2915 g.) was added to it. The resulting deep red solution on treatment with strong hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.) separated the dye in thick crystalline mass. More of glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) was added to the mixture and boiled for 15 minutes, filtered hot, washed with a little acetic acid and hot water. The product (1.7825 g., 81.4%) was crystallised from benzene in fine small thread-like darkish red needles. It is moderately soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and benzene. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a violet-red solution. It dyes wool in darkish red shade from an acid bath and cotton in the same shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found: C, 60.9 ; H, 2.6. $C_{16}H_6O_2NClS$ requires C, 61.2 ; H, 2.5 per cent).

3-(5-Chloro) indole-2'-(7'-chloro) thionaphthene-indigo was prepared in a similar way by boiling a solution of 5-chloro-isatin (0.5445 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) in glacial acetic acid (60 c. c.) and strong hydrochloric acid (5 c. c.) for 20 minutes. The sharp, needle-shaped, crystalline, silky, darkish red dye (0.969 g., 81.3%) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in long needles. It is soluble in aniline, moderately soluble in acetic acid, sparingly soluble in benzene, xylene and alcohol. The solution of this dye in strong sulphuric acid is violet. It dyes wool and cotton in darkish red shade. (Found : C, 54.7 ; H, 2.31. $C_{11}H_7O_2NCl_2S$ requires C, 55.1 ; H, 2.01 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo) indole-2'-(7'-chloro) thionaphthene-indigo.—The deep red solution, produced by dissolving 5-bromo-isatin (0.678 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) in boiling glacial acetic acid (65 c. c.) separated, on treatment with strong hydrochloric acid (4-5 c. c.) and boiling for 25 minutes, the darkish red, soft, needle-shaped crystals (1.093 g., 92.8%). It was crystallised from nitrobenzene in long needles. The solubility of this dye and also its dyeing shades on wool and on cotton resemble the preceding compound. (Found : C, 48.4 ; H, 1.92. $C_{11}H_7O_2NClBrS$ requires C, 48.9 ; H, 1.78 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(7'-chloro) thionaphthene-indigo was obtained in clusters of deep red needles (1.235 g., 87.3%) from a solution of 5:7-dibromo-isatin (0.915 g.) and 7-chloro-3 hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) in glacial acetic acid (75 c. c.) when treated with strong hydrochloric acid (4 c. c.) and boiled for 25 minutes. It was crystallised from pyridine in small wooly needles. It is sparingly soluble in xylene and more so in benzene and acetic acid. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a brick-red solution. It imparts a light violet-red shade to wool from an acid bath and violet-red shade to cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found : C, 40.4 ; H, 1.22. $C_{11}H_5O_2NClBr_2S$ requires C, 40.7 ; H, 1.27 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro)-indole-2'-(7'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigo.—5-Bromo-7-nitro-isatin (0.813 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) were dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid (90 c. c.) ; strong hydrochloric acid (3 c. c.) was added to the mixture and boiled for 15 minutes. The violet-red product (1.128 g., 86.1%) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in flaky crystals. It is moderately soluble in xylene, sparingly soluble in acetic acid. The solution of the substance in strong sulphuric acid is violet. It dyes wool in light violet shade from an acid bath and cotton in darkish violet-red shade from hydrosulphite vat. (Found C, 43.5 ; H, 1.05. $C_{11}H_5O_2N_2ClBrS$ requires C, 43.88 ; H, 1.37 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dinitro)indole-2'-(7'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigo was prepared by boiling a glacial acetic acid (85 c. c.) solution of 5:7-dinitro-isatin (0.711 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) and strong hydrochloric acid (4 c. c.) for 25 minutes. The violet-red dye (1.04 g., 86.6%) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in aggregate of small needles. It is sparingly soluble in xylene, acetic acid and more so in benzene. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a reddish violet solution. It imparts a violet-red shade to wool from an acid bath and darkish violet-red shade from the hydrosulphite vat. (Found : C, 47.3 ; H, 1.52. $C_{11}H_5O_2N_2ClS$ requires C, 47.58 ; H, 1.49 per cent).

7:7'-Dichlorothioindigo.—7-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (1.988 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (50 c. c., 10% approx.) and warmed on the water-bath and treated slowly with a solution of potassium ferricyanide (5%) until the precipitation of the symmetrical violet-red dye was complete (1.455 g., 79.8%). It was crystallised from nitrobenzene in long pointed needles melting above 320°. It is soluble in nitrobenzene, moderately soluble in xylene and sparingly soluble in acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride and benzene ; insoluble in alcohol. It dyes wool in light violet-red shade, although not fully developed from an acid bath and cotton in pleasant violet-red shade from the deep yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found : S, 17.0, 17.6. $C_{16}H_8O_2Cl_2S_2$ requires S, 17.54 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE, PATNA.

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